

ENSEMBLE

ENhanced AI-baSEd cybercriMe-oriented
collaBorative investigation technologies
and capabilitiEs

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Key Facts

Duration: November 2024 – October 2027

EU Contribution: € 3.663.143,00

Programme: Horizon Europe Programme

The Consortium

Coordinator: Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (Greece)

Partners: A multidisciplinary team of 18 organisations (including 2 associated partners) from 10 European countries, bringing together Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs), research institutions, and industry partners.

The Challenge

Technological advancements create opportunities for sophisticated cybercrimes that, through innovative tactics and techniques, pose serious security and financial risks to the EU and beyond. Combating cross-border cybercriminal activities requires a well-rounded response that goes beyond pure technology.

ENSEMBLE's primary objective is to provide exactly such a response, at the nexus of advanced AI-based technological solutions, multi-stakeholder investigation processes, training, and awareness. The project focuses on detecting and preventing ransomware, cyber fraud, data theft and extortion, unauthorised access, and crypto-jacking.

The Mission

The project's mission is to equip police authorities, prosecutors, and judicial actors with the tools and skills needed to effectively fight sophisticated cyber-threats across borders. Its core approach is built on a three-pillar strategy:

- **AI-Powered Investigation Toolbox:** Developing a modular, forensically sound toolbox based on user-centric criteria. This will assist Police Authorities in detecting, extracting, processing, and analysing online information relevant to cybercrime activities.
- **Capacity Building & Training:** Offering innovative training curricula and methods for Police Authorities, prosecutors, and judicial actors, aligned with their needs and covering technological, procedural, operational, and legal/multi-jurisdictional dimensions. This includes synchronous/asynchronous learning methodologies.
- **Public Awareness & Engagement:** Cultivating public awareness and engagement with relevant actors for early identification and prevention of cybercrimes through targeted awareness-raising campaigns and specific policy recommendations.

Additionally, the project capitalises on joint multi-stakeholder operations (national and cross-border) and secure data and information sharing mechanisms.

The Impact

ENSEMBLE AI-Based Investigation Toolbox

- **Modular & Forensically Sound:** A user-centric toolbox for detecting, extracting, processing, and analysing online evidence.
- **Targeted Threat Coverage:** Specifically addressing ransomware, cyber fraud, data theft, extortion, unauthorised access, and crypto-jacking (cryptocurrency mining malware).

Capacity Building & Training Programme

- **Innovative Curricula:** Tailored training for LEAs, prosecutors, and judicial actors on the technological, procedural, operational, and legal dimensions of cybercrime investigations.
- **Flexible Learning Methodologies:** Offering both synchronous and asynchronous learning to meet diverse operational needs.

Collaborative & Cross-Border Impact

- **Multi-Stakeholder Operations:** Enabling coordinated investigations at both national and cross-border levels through secure data and information sharing mechanisms.
- **Public Awareness Campaigns:** Targeted campaigns to help citizens and organisations identify and prevent cybercrime early.
- **Policy Recommendations:** Providing actionable recommendations to shape future EU cybercrime legislation and cooperation frameworks.